

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CLASSROOM ENVIRONMENT AND LEADERSHIP ABILITIES OF STUDENTS IN MIANWALI

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Abstract

In teaching learning process, leadership skills are important for personal and professional development of learners. The current study investigate the association between classroom atmosphere and leadership abilities of students. The research design implied in current study was survey research design with quantitative study type. Population for current research was grade 9th and 10th female students of district Mianwali and Bhakkar. Sample of the study was students from two schools of the above-mentioned districts through convenient sampling technique. Total data was collected from 401 secondary school students. The classroom environment scale was used to measure classroom organization and leadership ability scale was adopted in current study. Research instruments were translated also in Urdu language because secondary school students can easily understand this language. Data was collected physically by the researchers visits in selected schools of Government Girls High School Mianwali and Government Girls Elementary High School Kallur Kot, Bhakkar. Both instruments reliability was checked by Cronbach's alpha and result revealed both instruments were highly reliable in current study context. Pearson correlation and regression analysis were used for data analysis. The results revealed an significant relationship between classroom environment and leadership abilities. A significant effect classroom environment on leadership abilities was observed. The study recommends that to meet 21 century needs, educational institutes need to conduct workshops for teacher to promote the positive classroom organization and enhance leadership skills.

Introduction

Educational research consistently highlights the critical role of the classroom organization in shaping not only students' academic outcomes but also their leadership abilities. Fraser (1994) defines the classroom environment as a multidimensional construct encompassing the physical layout, instructional strategies, teacher-student interactions, peer collaboration, and the overall psychological climate. A positive classroom environment has been strongly linked with student motivation, active participation and opportunities for collaborative learning (Hamre & Pianta, 2007). These features are crucial for cultivating

leadership qualities such as confidence, responsibility, decision-making, communication and teamwork skills that extend beyond academics and prepare students for future personal and professional success. Leadership abilities represent a set of interpersonal and organizational skills that enable individuals to influence, motivate and guide others toward shared goals. These include decision-making, conflict resolution, communication, responsibility and the ability to inspire peers (Cocco, 2006). In the context of high schools, leadership development is especially important because it prepares students for future civic,

academic and career roles. However, in Pakistan, particularly in rural and semi-urban districts such as Mianwali and Bhakkar, the education system is heavily exam-oriented and often relies on rote memorization. There is minimal space for critical thinking, participatory learning, or chances for students to exercise leadership in the classroom with this method (Ahmad et al., 2019). Consequently, students frequently lack the fundamental leadership skills needed in today's workplace, even though they may do well on tests.

The classroom setting can be the starting point for leadership development since it offers both tangible and intangible elements that support student development. Both non-physical elements like teacher-student connections, classroom management, peer collaboration, and emotional climate, as well as physical elements like seating arrangements, classroom organization, and resources, have a direct impact on leadership opportunities (Barrett et al., 2015). Supportive classroom environments where teachers promote student involvement and decision-making, for instance, enable kids to take charge, work together on projects, and grow in responsibility all essential components of leadership. However, rigorous, teacher-centered settings limit student autonomy and engagement, which hinders the development of leadership.

There is much empirical support for the link between leadership skills and the classroom environment. Cooperative learning techniques, according to Johnson and Johnson (2009), enable students to assume leadership positions in group activities, which improves accountability and communication. According to Ahmad et al. (2019), leadership is closely linked to the teamwork, adaptability, and interpersonal competency that are fostered by Pakistani classrooms and schools with a positive culture. Additionally, structured peer collaboration improves decision-making and conflict resolution—two essential leadership skills, according to Gillies (2007). On the other hand, Sulaiman and Bakar (2019) observed that inadequately run classrooms with little assistance from teachers do not give students enough chances to take on leadership positions. Traditionally, more adaptable, student-centered methods have replaced strict, teacher-centered

models in educational settings. Traditional schools left little room for leadership or autonomy in favor of authority, discipline, and memorization (Cuban, 1993). However, education reformers such as John Dewey advocated for participatory and collaborative learning, encouraging students to take responsibility and engage in decision-making, which directly supports leadership development (Brooks & Brooks, 1999; Darling-Hammond et al., 2020). Contemporary classrooms now aim to create emotionally safe and inclusive spaces where students can practice leadership through active participation, peer mentoring and collaborative decision-making. Physical design elements, such as group seating and resource availability, further facilitate leadership opportunities (Barrett et al., 2015).

In Pakistan, and particularly in the rural districts of Mianwali and Bhakkar, little empirical research has been conducted on how classroom atmosphere influence the development of students' leadership abilities. Most local studies have focused on academic outcomes, neglecting leadership skills (Irshadullah, 2014). Given the limited extracurricular platforms for leadership training in these areas, the classroom often becomes the only environment where such abilities can be nurtured. This makes it essential to investigate the relationship between classroom environment and leadership abilities, providing much-needed evidence for teachers, administrators, and policymakers to reform practices and curricula. This study is significant in multiple respects. Practically, it highlights how teachers and school leaders can structure classroom environments to promote leadership among students, preparing them for 21st-century challenges. The study also provides policy-level implications, suggesting that educational reforms in Pakistan should move beyond rote learning to actively integrate leadership development within classroom practices. Theoretically, the research draws on Bandura's (1977) Social Learning Theory, which emphasizes the role of observation, modeling, and interaction in skill acquisition. The study advances our knowledge of how high school classroom environments can foster students' leadership abilities in this way.

The classroom environment is more than just a place to impart knowledge; it is a dynamic setting that molds students' abilities, dispositions, and leadership styles. Peer cooperation, classroom management, teacher-student interactions, and encouraging learning environments are all critical in educating students to become successful leaders. The classroom acquires an even greater significance in rural and semi-urban districts such as Mianwali and Bhakkar, where there are limited options for alternative leadership development. Thus, this study explores the connection between high school students' leadership skills and the classroom environment in an effort to offer insights that can guide Pakistani educational policy and practice.

Literature Review

The classroom atmosphere plays a critical impact in determining students' leadership potential as well as their academic performance, according to educational research. In addition to being a physical location for instruction, a classroom is a dynamic social, cognitive, and emotional setting where students engage with classmates, teachers, and educational materials (Fraser, 1994). Scholars contend that students' motivation, engagement, and chances to exercise leadership skills including communication, teamwork, accountability, and decision-making are all strongly impacted by the physical and social aspects of the classroom environment (Hamre & Pianta, 2007). Leadership abilities are increasingly recognized as critical for students' long-term personal and professional success, making the classroom a central environment for nurturing these capacities (Cocco, 2006). Leadership abilities refer to the competencies that enable individuals to guide, motivate, and collaborate with others toward achieving common objectives. These include communication, critical thinking, decision-making, responsibility, conflict resolution, and the ability to inspire peers (Cocco, 2006). Unlike technical knowledge or subject-specific abilities, leadership competencies are transferable across academic, social, and professional contexts. Bandura's (1977) Social Learning Theory highlights that leadership is developed through observation, modeling, and interaction, processes that are embedded within the

classroom environment. In Pakistan, however, particularly in rural and semi-urban districts such as Bhakkar and Mianwali, the education system remains largely exam-oriented, emphasizing rote memorization over student-centered learning (Irshadullah, 2014). As a result, while students may achieve strong academic performance, they often lack sufficient opportunities to practice leadership roles within classrooms.

The classroom environment consists of both physical and psychosocial dimensions that together create the conditions for leadership development. Physical elements include classroom design, seating arrangements, ventilation, and access to learning resources, all of which influence opportunities for group work and collaborative learning (Barrett et al., 2015). For instance, flexible seating and resource-rich environments facilitate peer interaction, allowing students to take initiative and practice leadership roles during discussions and projects. Psychological and social aspects, such as teacher-student relationships, peer interactions, classroom management, and emotional climate, are equally important (Fraser, 1994; Pianta et al., 2012). Students who have supportive relationships are more confident and feel like they belong, which empowers them to take an active role in leadership and decision-making activities. On the other hand, inflexible, authoritarian, or teacher-dominated classrooms restrict autonomy and interaction, which impedes the development of leadership skills (Cuban, 1993).

Additionally, empirical data supports the close relationship between leadership skills and classroom conditions. According to Johnson and Johnson (2009), cooperative learning techniques give students the chance to take on leadership positions in their groups in addition to encouraging cooperation and communication. Similar to this, Ahmad et al. (2019) emphasized that in Pakistani schools, a supportive classroom environment fosters cooperation, accountability, and interpersonal skills—all of which are critical elements of leadership. Group-based learning exercises also improve leadership, decision-making, and conflict resolution skills, according to Gillies (2007). Sulaiman and Bakar (2019), on the other hand, found that students are less likely to

exhibit leadership behaviors in classes with low levels of teacher support and active involvement. This suggests that classroom conditions alone are inadequate in the absence of peer collaboration and mentorship.

Classroom models have changed over time in ways that have a big impact on leadership development. The emphasis on authority, discipline, and memorization in traditional classrooms restricted students' freedom and ability to make their own decisions (Cuban, 1993). Reformers like Dewey, on the other hand, placed a strong emphasis on participatory learning, which paved the way for students to develop their leadership skills by urging them to take charge and share responsibility (Brooks & Brooks, 1999). Constructivist methods place a strong emphasis on experience and group learning, which are closely related to developing leadership skills (Richardson, 2003; Darling-Hammond et al., 2020). The importance of diversity, emotional safety, and teamwork in fostering student leadership is becoming more widely acknowledged in today's schools (Pianta et al., 2012).

Interactions between teachers and students are particularly important for leadership development. Teachers who are understanding and supportive foster trust, promote student initiative, and offer forums for making decisions and resolving issues (Wentzel, 1997). Structured group activities and project-based learning foster opportunities for students to exercise leadership by guiding peers, resolving conflicts, and organizing collaborative tasks (Gillies, 2007). Classroom management strategies also reinforce leadership by setting clear expectations, establishing routines, and allowing students to take responsibility within those frameworks (Emmer & Evertson, 2016). On the contrary, disorganized or overly rigid management discourages autonomy, thereby restricting leadership opportunities.

In Pakistan's rural and semi-urban contexts, where extracurricular leadership platforms are limited, the classroom becomes the primary site for cultivating leadership abilities. Yet, most schools in regions such as Mianwali and Bhakkar still prioritize examination performance over student-centered leadership opportunities (Irshadullah, 2014). This creates a gap between students' academic achievements

and their readiness for future civic and professional roles. Investigating the role of classroom environments in leadership development is thus highly significant, as it can provide evidence-based guidance for teachers, school leaders, and policymakers to foster holistic student growth in under-researched educational contexts.

On the basis of above literature following hypothesis were made:

H_{A1}: There is a significant relationship between classroom environment and leadership abilities of students.

H_{A2} : The classroom environment is a significant predictor of students' leadership abilities.

Methodology

Quantitative survey design was used to investigate the correlation between classroom environment and leadership skills. The female students in Grades 9 and 10 from two government high schools in Bhakkar and Mianwali were selected as population for current research. Convenience sampling was employed and involved 401 students. Classroom Environment Scale was developed by Irshadullah (2014), with items related to fairness, inclusivity, working together, and support. Leadership Skills Scale was developed by Cocco (2006), assessing initiative, communication and working together. Both the scales were rated on a 5-point Likert scale. Pilot test reliability analysis provided Cronbach's alpha values of 0.85 (CE) and 0.79 (LA). Questionnaires were administered in person to collect the data. SPSS was utilized to perform Pearson correlation, and linear regression analysis.

Results

Table 1

Correlation between Classroom Environment and Leadership Abilities

Variable	Leadership Abilities	
Classroom Environment	Pearson correlation	.651
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001
	N	401

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

In above table pearson correlation analysis revealed a strong positive relationship between Classroom Environment (CE) and Leadership Abilities (LA) among the participants ($r = .651$, $p < .001$). This indicates that as students perceive their classroom environment to be more supportive, inclusive, and engaging, their leadership skills tend to increase

correspondingly. The correlation was statistically significant at the 0.01 level, confirming the reliability of this association in the sample of 401 students. Therefore alternate hypothesis were accepted.

Effect of Classroom Environment on the Leadership Abilities of students

Table 2

Model summary of Linear Regression Analysis

R	R ²	F	Adjusted R ²	S.E.
.651 ^a	.424	293.217	.422	5.43266

The model summary reflected in Table 2 showed the value of $F = 293.217$ and $R^2 = 0.424$, which meant that 42.4% of the variation in the dependent variable (Leadership Abilities) was explained by the variation in the independent variable (Classroom Environment). Therefore, this model slightly exceeded the acceptable threshold and indicated that Classroom

Environment had a moderate to strong predictive ability. The remaining 57.6% of the variation in Leadership Abilities was attributed to other factors that were not included in the model. Based on these results, it was concluded that Classroom Environment significantly predicted Leadership Abilities and contributed to their development.

Table 3

Linear Regression Analysis of Classroom Environment on Leadership Abilities

Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardize Coefficients	t	Sig.
	Beta	Std. E	B		
(Constant)	14.479	1.542		9.390	.001
CE	0.638	0.037	0.651	17.124	.001

Table 3 presented the coefficients of the regression model. The unstandardized coefficient (B) for Classroom Environment (CE) was 0.638, which indicated that for every one-unit increase in Classroom Environment, Leadership Abilities increased by 0.638 units, assuming all other variables remained constant. The standardized beta coefficient was 0.651, suggesting a strong and positive effect of

Classroom Environment on Leadership Abilities. The t-value was 17.124, and the p-value was $< .001$, which was statistically significant at the $p < .05$ level. Since the beta was not equal to zero ($\beta \neq 0$) and the p-value was highly significant, the Alternative hypothesis was accepted. These findings confirmed alternate hypothesis that classroom environment had a

statistically significant and strong positive impact on the Leadership Abilities of students.

Discussion

The present study aim to explore :The Relationship Between Classroom Environment and Leadership Abilities of High School Students in Mianwali, Pakistan”. The correlation analysis revealed a strong positive relationship between classroom environment and leadership abilities ($r = .651, p < .001$). This finding suggests that students who perceive their classrooms as supportive, inclusive, and participatory are more likely to display leadership traits such as initiative, teamwork, and effective communication. These results are in line with Johnson and Johnson (2009), who demonstrated that cooperative learning structures enhance student leadership through improved teamwork and conflict resolution. According to Gillies (2007), collaborative learning exercises in the classroom greatly increased students' capacity for initiative and leadership. In contrast, several studies offer opposing viewpoints. Susanti and Hasanah (2017) contended that without the assistance of specialized mentorship and effective teacher facilitation, the classroom setting might not be enough to foster leadership. According to Balaji and Somashekar (2009), community involvement and extracurricular activities frequently have a greater impact on leadership development than classroom interactions. Although the school setting has an impact, these opposing viewpoints suggest that leadership skills may also necessitate complementing contexts like exposure to extracurricular activities and family participation.

Regression analysis provided more evidence of the classroom environment's predictive impact on leadership skills. These results are in line with Fraser's (1994) contention that structured and encouraging learning environments are ideal for fostering the growth of leadership and interpersonal abilities. Ahmad et al. (2019) discovered that students' leadership-oriented behaviors, teamwork, and responsibility were all enhanced by a positive classroom culture in Pakistani schools. But other academics bring up important issues. According to Barrett et al. (2015), physical aspects of a classroom, like lighting, ventilation, and space, can occasionally

have a greater impact on student achievement than social elements. Similarly, Sulaiman and Bakar (2019) noted that the classroom environment by itself might not be able to predict significant leadership development in the absence of emotional safety and active engagement techniques. These conflicting results show that although the classroom environment is a strong predictor, contextual elements like teacher preparation, resource availability, and school infrastructure may affect how effective the setting is.

Conclusion

The current study's findings showed that high school students' leadership abilities are significantly and favorably influenced by their classroom environment. Crucial leadership qualities like communication, teamwork, decision-making, and problem-solving are fostered in an inclusive, encouraging, and interactive learning environment. Students are more likely to develop the self-assurance and abilities required for initiative and leadership roles in the academic, personal, and professional spheres when teachers foster teamwork, respect, and emotional safety. The results also highlight how relationships and classroom practices may be a powerful tool for preparing students for the demands and obligations of the twenty-first century. The classroom setting has a major impact on students' leadership skills.

Recommendations

Following recommendations were made on the basis of conclusions of this study:

- 1) This study recommends that teachers need to conduct regular seminars for professional development so they may establish encouraging, interactive classroom environments and actively engage students through debates, group projects, and peer-led sessions.
- 2) Examine the combined effects of classroom climate, extracurricular activities, and home environment on leadership, including longitudinal tracking and comparisons across gender, school type, and rural urban contexts.
- 3) Use both quantitative and qualitative methods such as surveys, interviews, and

focus groups to explore teacher and student perspectives on leadership development and to identify context-specific strategies for improvement.

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